

PROSPECTS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN

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***Annotation:** The article contains suggestions, opinions and comments on the establishment of free economic zones and their effective functioning in the development of the national and world economy and the intensification of international economic integration of the national economy.*

***Key words:** Free economic zone, technopark, cluster, Special economic zone, local personnel, Free trade zone, Small industrial zone.*

Introduction. Free economic zone is a territory created for the purpose of rapid socio-economic development of regions and sectors of the economy, attracting investments, as well as their use as a regional method of modernization and diversification of the economy and the introduction of modern technologies in the economic structure.

The results of analysis and discussion. A free trade zone is a class of special economic zone. It is a geographic area where goods may be imported, stored, handled, manufactured, or reconfigured and re-exported under specific customs regulation and generally not subject to customs duty. Free trade zones are generally organized around major seaports, international airports, and national frontiers – areas with many geographic advantages for trade. In the world economy it is closely connected with the material well-being of the people, their way of life, in many respects the establishment and functioning of free economic zones. In a country where there are broad incentives for foreign investment and entrepreneurship, as well as practical assistance and opportunities to rebuild the economy, both the amount of investment and the entrepreneurial ability of entrepreneurs will be high. For many developing countries, free economic zones are in fact a special area that promotes the concentration of living standards, production capacity of workers in the territory. As our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said “If we can carefully formulate investment projects by regions and sectors for investors who want to

invest in our economy, we can achieve a positive result in this matter. In this regard, it is necessary to organize and legally regulate the placement of business entities in free economic zones and small industrial zones, as well as giving them privileges and preferences”.

In the formation and improvement of the mechanism of state regulation of the establishment of free economic zones, the issue of principles and conduct of economic, including investment activities of enterprises and organizations located in free economic zones is considered important.

Currently, small industrial zones are one of the effective ways to develop small business and support it from the state. Small industrial zones are areas intended for the location of business entities, which include engineering-communication and infrastructure facilities, a certain land area or production area. Small industrial zones create great opportunities for the development of the areas where they are located.

As of April 1, 2022, there are 20 special economic zones, 116 small industrial zones, 12 technological parks, and 440 clusters aimed at the development of various sectors of the economy in our country. 512 in the zone, 1865 in the small industrial zone, 58 in the technological parks and 446 in the clusters.

As of April 1, 2022, the number of special economic zones, small industrial zones, technoparks and clusters by region¹

Table 1

	Total	Including			
		Special economic zone	Small industrial zone	Technopark	Cluster
Republic of Uzbekistan	588	20	116	12	440
Regions:					
Republic of Karakalpakstan	71	1	11	-	59

¹ State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Andijan	19	1	2	1	15
Bukhara	55	2	1	1	51
Jizzakh	33	2	1	-	30
Kashkadarya	41	-	8	-	33
Navoi	56	1	1	2	52
Namangan	50	2	28	-	20
Samarkand	43	1	1	-	41
Surkhandarya	61	2	22	-	37
Syrdarya	36	2	5	-	29
Tashkent	39	4	17	-	18
Fergana	21	1	10	-	10
Khorezm	54	1	1	7	45
Tashkent city	9	-	8	1	-

It is important to pay special attention to the conditions that play an important role in the development of free economic zones. These conditions may include:

- Convenient transport and geographical location of the region;
- Availability of developed production and infrastructure;
- Solid legal basis for the establishment of free economic zones;
- To guarantee the safety of their investments by the state to local and foreign investors and to create a favorable investment environment for their use;
- Wide coverage of the favorable conditions created for the implementation of business activities in free economic zones and actively carry out propaganda work.

Based on the facilities created in our republic for many years, it can be said that Uzbekistan has the following conditions for attracting foreign investors:

- Political stability;
- Formation of a legal framework protecting private property and competition;
- Establishment of infrastructure supporting the investment process;

- Convenient geographical location of the country;
- High development potential of the agro-industrial sector and country’s wealth of mineral resources;
- Availability of highly qualified labor resources;
- Sufficient width of the domestic market for trade.

Currently, three special economic zones are operating in Uzbekistan – free economic zone “Navoi” in Navoi region, free economic zone “Angren” in Tashkent region and free economic zone “Jizzakh” in Jizzakh region with the branch in Syrdarya region.

Conclusions and suggestions. We believe that it is necessary to further activate the attraction of foreign investments in free economic zones for the development of the economy of the region and the country and, on this basis, to further increase the export potential of the economy in the regions, and for this, the following should be implemented.

1. Work aimed at developing long-term programs for the development of sectors that will allow further strengthening of the economy in the region and increasing the participation of foreign investments in their implementation.
2. To provide financing with the participation of foreign investments for programs that create and increase employment based on the most modern digital technologies in production and industrialization, and prepare final products for domestic and foreign markets from raw materials created in the regions.
3. It is necessary to develop measures for the effective use of foreign investments through the development of regional infrastructures.
4. In order to expand or improve the activities of enterprises established with the participation of foreign investments, it is necessary to provide new technologies at the expense of international leasing and thereby establish international leasing relations in the regions and introduce a system of state promotion of these relations.

Therefore, the establishment of free economic zones and the expansion of their capabilities will find solutions to macro-economic issues of public importance.

Among others, we include accelerating the level of economic growth, updating and modernizing the industry, modernization, saturating the domestic market with high-quality products and services.

Literature.

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